

DANCAVAS working paper:

The impact of population screening for cardiovascular disease on quality of life

Rikke Søgaard¹, Axel Diederichsen², Jes Lindholt³

¹ Institute of Clinical Research, University of Southern Denmark, Odense, Denmark

² Department of Cardiothoracic and Vascular Surgery, Odense University Hospital, Odense, Denmark

³ Department of Cardiology, Odense University Hospital, Odense, Denmark

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Corresponding author

Rikke Søgaard

Institute of Clinical Research, J.B. Winsløvs Vej 4, 5000 Odense C, Denmark

E-mail rsoegaard@health.sdu.dk

Key words

Screening, quality of life

Abstract

Objective To examine the impact of population screening-generated events on quality of life: invitation, positive test result, initiation of preventive medication, enrolment in follow up at surgical department, and surgical repair.

Method A difference-in-difference design based on data collected alongside two randomised controlled trials where general population men were randomised to screening for cardiovascular disease or to no screening. Repeated measurements of quality of life were conducted up to three years after inclusion using all relevant scales of the EQ5D: the anxiety/depression item, the profile index (using Danish preference weights) and the visual analogue scale for global health. We compare the mean change scores from before to after events for groups experiencing versus not experiencing the events. Propensity score matching is additionally used to provide both unmatched and matched results.

Results Invitees reported to be marginally better off than non-invitees on all scales of the EQ5D. For events of receiving the test result, initiating preventive medication, being enrolled in surveillance and undergoing surgical repair, we observed no impact on overall quality of life but a minor impact of being enrolled in surveillance on emotional distress, which did not persist after matching.

Conclusion The often-claimed detrimental consequences of screening to quality of life could not be generally confirmed. Individual assessment of key events revealed only two possible consequences: a reassurance effect after a negative screening test and a minor negative impact to emotional distress of being enrolled in surveillance that did not spill over to overall quality of life.

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Summary

What is already known on this topic

Screening for cardiovascular disease is increasingly considered as future population programmes for prevention of disease and inequality in health. Yet, such programmes can only be recommended if their benefit net of any harm is positive – and that is currently uncertain with respect to possible harm to emotional functioning and quality of life.

What this study adds

We analyse the impact of the key events flowing from screening – receiving the invitation, receiving the test result, initiating preventive medication, being enrolled in surveillance and undergoing preventive surgery – and find no evidence of harm except for after enrolment in surveillance amongst those tested positive.

How this study might affect research, practice or policy

The findings inform the ethical considerations about the net benefit of screening and should also be included in the estimation of quality-adjusted life years of future cost effectiveness evaluations informing health policy.

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Introduction

Population screening programmes involve a number of ethical dilemmas in that an often-large number of healthy individuals have to be bothered in order to detect the typically fewer, who may benefit from detection of asymptomatic disease.[1, 2] Already by an invitation for screening, individuals are made aware of being in a target group and thus at higher risk for the target disease than their non-invited counterparts. The consequence of such awareness to quality of life (QoL) is probably marginal but a large number of invitees are affected such that the total harm could add up. After screening, individuals with a negative test may feel reassured whereas individuals with a positive test may experience both ups and downs related to the sudden status of being sick, having to take pills, having to attend follow ups or even having to undergo preventive surgery. These ups and downs possibly affect QoL but there is limited evidence from the actual screening context.

The current and limited evidence on the impact of screening on QoL is primarily from the cancer context and focus on screening for lung cancer[3, 4, 5, 6, 7], cervical cancer[8, 9, 10, 11], breast cancer[12, 13] and prostate cancer[14, 15]. This evidence generally suggests that attenders at screening may be better off QoL-wise than non-attenders, and that QoL may be temporarily affected after a positive screening test. There is, however, uncertainty as to whether such impacts are due to (healthier) individuals' self-selection into screening participation or actual consequences of screening. Further, there is even higher uncertainty as to whether the findings from the cancer context can be generalised to a context for cardiovascular disease (CVD).

One noteworthy difference between CVD and cancer screening in relation to any impact on QoL is the consequence of a positive test. Early detection of cancer usually has a curative target, and a high-intensity regimen of diagnostics, staging and therapy follow within a short time frame. Detection of CVD, on the other hand, usually means that life-long and often low-intensity, pharmacological prophylactic therapy is recommended to moderate cardiovascular risk factors and prevent future events including diabetes. The fact that the prevalence as well as the preventive potential is a lot bigger for CVD than it is for cancer adds to the potential impact of CVD screening on QoL. And, it underlines the need for specific evidence to inform the current considerations about new programs including screening for abdominal aortic aneurysms, familiar hypercholesterolaemia, hypertension, atrial fibrillation, coronary artery calcification and type 2 diabetes.[16]

One exception to the list of new CVD screening programmes without real-world evidence is screening for abdominal aortic aneurysms, which has already been implemented in Sweden, England, Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland, Ireland, Germany, and is recommended for ever-smokers in the US.[16] From the QoL studies reported alongside these national programmes, it is suggested that a positive test result is associated with a short-term negative impact on QoL.[17] There is divergent evidence with respect to any emotional distress of being enrolled in ultrasound surveillance with a small AAA.[18, 19] What is clear from these reports, however, is that a longitudinal and controlled design is warranted for valid estimates of a causal impact of screening on QoL. Further, these reports provide an incomplete foundation in that important events such as invitation, initiation of pharmacological therapy and preventive surgical repair remain unaddressed.

The objective of this study is to examine the impact of population screening-generated events on QoL: invitation, positive test result, initiation of prophylactic pharmacological therapy, enrolment in surveillance scheme at surgical department, and surgical repair.

Methods

Study design

We use a difference-in-difference (DID) design to estimate the mean difference between groups, experiencing versus not experiencing the screening-generated events, in their differences over time: from before to after for those experiencing the event and over a similar period of time for those not experiencing the event.

The design piggy-back on two randomised controlled screening trials including all men aged 60-74 and living in the region of South Denmark from 2014 to 2019.[20] These trials generated the screening events and included baseline QoL measurements for all invited to screening and a 20% random sample of those not invited for screening (see figure 1). Repeated measurements were conducted in annual rounds during the second quarter each year, from 2015 through 2018. Due to the staggered inclusion into the trials, not everybody was invited for repeated measurements of QoL. In the current design, we take advantage of the scale of measurements and, for each event of interest, we sample individuals with before- and after-event measurements and use the DID design to control for risk selection as well as secular trends.

The DID design is a quasi-experimental design, which is commonly used to study causal relationships in social sciences when randomisation is infeasible or unethical.[21] In the current case, it is infeasible to randomize to events except for the invitation (where randomisation was actually conducted). The before- and after-event difference control for selection, which is stable over time, whereas the comparison with a control group's before- and after-event differences control for secular trends. The DID design provides unbiased effect estimates when the before-after difference would have been the same between the event and the non-event groups in the absence of event. This is referred to as the identifying assumption. It should be noted that it is not necessary that the groups have similar before-levels of QoL or similar individual characteristics unless these accelerate or decelerate the difference over time. E.g., estimates of the effect of a positive screening test will be unbiased despite negatives being in better health than positives, as long as their change scores would have been parallel in the absence of a test result. In cases where the identifying assumption appears unreasonably strong, it can be relaxed by combining the DID design with analytical weighting[21, 22], as described below.

Comparators

We assess the impact of five major events generated by screening: receiving an invitation with information about risk (yes/no, assessed amongst all), receiving the test result (positive/negative, assessed amongst all attenders), initiation of preventive medication (yes/no, assessed amongst all with a positive test and no use of preventive medication within the most recent six months), enrolment in surveillance to monitor the need for surgical repair (enrolled/not enrolled, assessed amongst all with indication for surveillance)

and preventive surgical repair (yes/no, assessed amongst all with indication for surveillance).

Sampling and data sources

The comparators are specified from actual event dates in the event group, and for the no event groups without date (no initiation, no surveillance, no surgical repair), a synthetic date data was constructed based on the means for the event groups. For each event, we then look up any before and after QoL measurements in the trial data and include individuals in the current study if they have a before and an after measurement. Event status, event date, EQ5D measurements and smoking status are informed from the trial data. This is supplemented with demographics and socioeconomic status from national registry data.

EQ5D

All measurements are undertaken using the three-level health profile and the visual analogue scale (VAS) of the EQ5D.[23] By this instrument, the respondent is asked to choose the statement that 'best describes your health TODAY', either by a profile of five health dimensions with each three response levels (e.g., I have no problems in walking about, I have some problems in walking about or I am confined to bed) or to mark a level on a global health VAS. The profile can be analysed for individual dimensions (based on an assigned score of 1 to 3) or weighted into a profile index based on preference weights.[24] The VAS allows the respondent to directly rate his or her health on a scale from 0-100 where zero indicates 'the worst health you can imagine' and 100 'the best health you can imagine'.

Due to the focus on emotional distress in relation to screening, we analyse 1) the single item focussing on anxiety and depression (item, range 1-3 with higher values representing more distress), the health profile weighted into an index using Danish preference weights (index, range -0.59 to 1 with higher values representing higher QoL), and the direct observations of the VAS (VAS, range 0-100 with higher values representing better health). It should be noted that the three scales are conceptually different and focus on: 1) emotional distress related to anxiety and depression, 2) utility from health-related QoL and 3) global health.

Statistical analysis

Population characteristics for each of the five event-based sets of comparators are assessed by frequencies and chi2 tests for categorical variables and by means and t-tests for continuous variables.

For the main analyses of the impact of events, we report parallel results of unmatched and matched DID estimates. The matched results are based on 1:1 nearest neighbour propensity score matching with a focus on key factors that may affect QoL and change unevenly between the groups over time: current smoker (yes/no), living alone (yes/no), working (yes/no), household income (quartile dummies) and self-reported global health (continuous). In addition, age (continuous) was added to the models where the no event date was synthetic. Propensity scores are estimated from probit regression and separately for each event and for each of the QoL scales due to slight differences in the within-event response to the different QoL scales. The distributions of the propensity scores are evaluated graphically (appendix figures 1-5) and the balancing of covariates after matching

is assessed by the percentage bias (appendix tables 1-5). For calculation of standard errors, we take into account that the propensity scores are estimated.[25]

For each of the event and no event groups, we report the mean before-, after- and change score over time with standard errors (SE). For the main results of the DID estimators, we report the unmatched and the matched means with 95% confidence intervals (CI).

Research ethics

All analyses are conducted on anonymised data and in conformity with the General Data Protection Act (approvals 14/9140 and 17/5994). We conform to good practice guidelines for reporting.[26]

Public involvement

This study has been preceded by interviews and preference elicitation among screening participants. It has been discussed with patient representatives from the Department of cardiology at the Odense University Hospital.

Results

This study included 33769 men from two screening trials, who were invited to report their QoL at least once. More than 94% of the individuals who were in contact with the screening staff responded to the first measurement (table 1). Exceptions were non-invitees with 35% response and non-attenders who dragged the overall response in the invited group down to 69%. Response rates to repeated measurements were affected by not everybody being invited to respond due to the study design of annual survey rounds until 2018 even though the trials included participants until 2019. The listed response rates are thus minimum rates and not adjusted for the pseudo-random sampling due to trial design. Baseline characteristics and their differences between the groups of events and no events are as expected and will be taken into account by the analytical strategy as detailed below.

For each of the comparators, propensity score models are specified to balance the baseline differences that could change over time at an uneven speed. Despite smaller n as the events become more severe, the propensity score matching reasonably balanced the key covariates (detailed results in appendix tables 1-5). No statistically significant bias remained after matching and there was common support for all observations (appendix figures 1-5).

Receiving an invitation for screening appears to be associated with statistically significant reduced emotional distress ($p < 0.001$) and increased QoL ($p < 0.001$). This is consistent across the matched and the unmatched estimators and corresponds to a relative reduction in emotional distress of around 2% and a relative increase in QoL of around 3% (table 2).

Receiving a positive screening test result does not impact emotional distress or QoL, which is again consistent across the unmatched and matched DID estimators (table 3). At baseline, those ending with a positive test had higher emotional distress and poorer QoL than those ending with a negative test, but their trends over time appear to be parallel. In terms of global health, there is a tendency for those testing negative to actually improve over time on the unmatched DID estimator, which corresponds to around 1% change relative to

baseline. After matching, this becomes statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) and is estimated to 1.62 point on the global health scale from 0-100, which corresponds to around 2% increase as a probable reassurance effect on self-perceived health.

The most common outcome of CVD screening is a recommendation for initiation of preventive medication such as antihypertensives, statins and antithrombotic agents. Initiation of preventive medication does not appear to impact emotional distress or QoL (table 4) but global health is impacted negatively with up to 2.72 points, which corresponds to a 3% reduction. The fact that the impact is isolated on the physical health scale and not the emotional or general quality of life suggest that the impact could be related to possible side-effects of medication.

Enrolment in surveillance at a surgical centre reflects a more severe diagnosis than the comparator of having a positive test (with indication for preventive medication only). Across all of the unmatched and matched DID estimators, the only consequence of enrolment appears to be an around 7% increase in emotional distress (DID estimator 0.08, 95% CI 0.01;0.14, $p = 0.018$), which reduces to around 5% and becomes statistically insignificant after matching (DID estimator 0.06, 95% CI -0.03;0.15, $p = 0.193$).

Elective surgical repair is the least common but possibly also the most serious event that flow from screening. Nevertheless, we observe that the event and no event groups follow remarkably similar trends over time on all scales (table 6). If anything, there is a non-significant tendency for the no event group deteriorating more over time on the global health than the event group.

Discussion

In this DID design piggy-backing on two large population screening trials, we found that invitees report to be better off than non-invitees whereas the often-claimed emotional distress related to screening participation or the events flowing thereof such as receiving the test result, initiation of preventive medication, enrolment in surveillance programs or undergoing preventive surgical repair appears to be limited. In fact, the only consequences observed were a possible reassurance effect after a negative screening test, and a possible impact to emotional distress of being enrolled in surveillance that did however not spill over to overall QoL.

To the best of our knowledge this is the first study to examine the impact of individual screening events on QoL in a causal DID design. This design originates from social science but is increasingly recognised also in CVD.[27] Unbiased estimates of the possible harm of screening is of high importance for ethical as well as for health policy reasons as decision makers are increasingly considering evidence for cost effectiveness based on quality-adjusted life years (QALY). The QALY typically captures the benefit of screening by the mortality risk reduction whereas the harm to QoL is much less straightforward because it may fluctuate over time as individual events are faced. With the QALY being an area-under-the-curve measure, assumptions are required for every day QoL is not directly measured. The present study captures the average impact for an average of six months after the events (due to the annual measurement rounds). For a precise reflection of the fluctuation in QoL

over time, hundreds of repeated measurements would be required – or indeed a qualitative design identifying when and how often measurements would be needed.

The usual concern about selection bias due to non-response apply. Dedicated trial staff ensured very high response rates to the first measurement round but due to the study design, which was based on annual rounds which ended before the trials did, not everybody was invited to reply to repeated measurements. We consider this cause of non-response for pseudo-random and thus not necessarily an issue to selection bias. We further choose one of the strongest designs for tackling selection with a combination of the DID design where unobserved heterogeneity cancels out as long as it is stable, and propensity score matching where we included both life style (smoking), living conditions (SES) and self-perceived health. Nevertheless, poor response rates to the repeated measurements for the events which fall late after screening is a possible weakness to the study.

One important finding is that preventive surgical repair does not seem to affect future QoL, which would otherwise be a serious harm. This is in consensus with the results of an early study conducted alongside the UK small aneurysm trial[28] and could mask a complex network of emotions from relief of the uncertainty related to surveillance to handling the mortality risk associated with surgery. The strength of this study is not to disentangle such emotions but to provide a valid average estimate in order to strengthen the foundation for policy making. The use of the EQ5D is another strength due to this instrument's popularity and well established psychometric properties.[29] In line with many screening studies trying to balance ease of response with sensitivity of instruments, we used the three-level version of the EQ5D. This is however also the main limitation of the study in that a five-level version has been developed because of concern about sensitivity of the three-level version.

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Ethics approval

This is an observational study that does not require ethics approval according to the Danish Research Ethics Committee.

Consent to participate

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Competing interests

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

Contributorship

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Data collection was managed by JSL and AD. Data analysis and the first draft was made by RS. All authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript and approved the final manuscript. RS is responsible for the overall content as guarantor.

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Table 1 Characteristics of the study populations used for assessment of impact of screening-generated events

	Invitation		Test result		Enrolment surveillance		Initiation medication		Surgical repair	
	Event	No event	Event	No event						
Response to first measurement	15704 (69)	3861 (35)	8457 (>99)	5684 (>99)	872 (100)	7596 (>99)	2354 (94)	505 (>99)	440 (95)	789 (>99)
Response repeated measurements	NA	NA	4154 (49)	2753 (48)	113 (13)	3492 (46)	1049 (45)	248 (49)	72 (16)	605 (77)
Age in years (mean, SE)	67 (0.03)	66 (0.06)	67 (0.06)	66 (0.07)	69 (0.29)	66 (0.07)	66 (0.12)	65 (0.24)	69 (0.42)	68 (0.14)
Current smoker	2287 (16)	NA	742 (18)	276 (10)	23 (20)	593 (17)	220 (21)	38 (15)	16 (23)	127 (21)
Living alone	2701 (17)	750 (19)	701 (17)	364 (13)	15 (13)	580 (17)	167 (16)	50 (20)	14 (20)	106 (18)
Education										
Lower secondary	3451 (22)	861 (22)	901 (22)	195 (19)	26 (23)	753 (22)	195 (19)	46 (19)	17 (24)	134 (22)
0-3 years further	8332 (53)	2020 (52)	2220 (53)	575 (55)	62 (55)	1863 (54)	579 (55)	114 (46)	38 (53)	331 (55)
>3 years further	3921 (25)	980 (25)	1033 (25)	275 (26)	25 (22)	876 (25)	275 (26)	88 (35)	17 824	140 (23)
Working	6147 (39)	1878 (49)	1677 (40)	1368 (50)	22 (19)	1502 (43)	509 (49)	126 (51)	20 (28)	164 (27)
Household income										
1 st quartile	2750 (18)	677 (18)	995 (17)	313 (11)	13 (12)	573 (16)	159 (15)	33 (13)	17 (24)	112 (19)
2 nd quartile	4305 (27)	923 (24)	1142 (27)	640 (23)	41 (36)	925 (26)	242 (23)	59 (24)	19 (26)	197 (33)
3 rd quartile	4373 (28)	1045 (27)	1179 (28)	787 (29)	38 (34)	1000 (29)	307 (29)	73 (29)	22 (31)	162 (27)
4 th quartile	4256 (27)	1216 (31)	1138 (27)	1013 (37)	21 (19)	994 (28)	341 (33)	83 (33)	14 (19)	134 (22)
Self-rated global health										
0-100 (mean, SE)	81 (0.12)	81 (0.27)	80 (0.23)	84 (0.25)	79 (1.37)	80 (0.26)	84 (0.37)	86 (0.72)	77 (2.11)	80 (0.60)

NA=not available, SE=standard error

Note: values are n (%) unless otherwise stated. Statistically significant differences at p<0.05 are bolded.

Table 2 The impact of invitation for screening on quality of life

	Invited n	Non invited n	Difference	
			Unmatched mean (95% CI)	Matched mean (95% CI)
EQ5D	mean (SE)	mean (SE)		
Item	15675	3845	-0.02	-0.03
	1.12 (<0.01)	1.14 (<0.01)	(-0.03;-0.01)	(-0.04;-0.01)
Index	15594	3803	0.03	0.03
	0.90 (<0.01)	0.87 (<0.01)	(0.02; 0.04)	(0.03; 0.04)
VAS	15537	3724	-0.29	-0.10
	81.18 (0.12)	81.41 (0.27)	(-0.84;0.27)	(-0.19;<0.01)

EQ5D=EuroQol 5-dimension, SE=standard error, CI=confidence interval, VAS=Visual analogue scale.

Statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$ are bolded.

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Table 3 The impact of the screening test result on quality of life amongst those who attend screening

		Positive	Negative	DID	
		n	n	Unmatched	Matched
EQ5D		mean (SE)	mean (SE)	mean (95% CI)	mean (95% CI)
Item	Before	4127	2737		
		1.13 (<0.01)	1.10 (<0.01)		
	After	4127	2737		
		1.14 (<0.01)	1.10 (<0.01)		
	Difference	4127	2737	<0.01	<0.01
		0.01 (0.01)	<0.01 (0.01)	(-0.01;0.02)	(-0.02;0.02)
Index	Before	4059	2693		
		0.89 (<0.01)	0.92 (<0.01)		
	After	4059	2693		
		0.88 (<0.01)	0.91 (<0.01)		
	Difference	4059	2693	<0.01	<0.01
		-0.01 (<0.01)	-0.01 (<0.01)	(-0.01;<0.01)	(-0.01;0.01)
VAS	Before	3996	2690		
		80.46 (0.23)	83.93 (0.24)		
	After	3996	2690		
		80.58 (0.25)	84.53 (0.25)		
	Difference	3996	2690	-0.47	-1.62
		0.13 (0.20)	0.60 (0.21)	(-1.06;0.12)	(-2.33;-0.91)

EQ5D=EuroQol 5-dimension, SE=standard error, DID=difference-in-difference, CI=confidence interval, VAS=Visual analogue scale.

Statistically significant differences at $p < 0.05$ are bolded.

Table 4 The impact of initiation of preventive medication on quality of life amongst those with a positive test who did not use preventive medication before screening

		Initiation	No initiation	DID	
		n	n	Unmatched	Matched
		mean (SE)	mean (SE)	mean (95% CI)	mean (95% CI)
EQ5D	Item	1043	246		
	Before	1.09 (0.01)	1.07 (0.02)		
	After	1.09 (0.01)	1.09 (0.02)		
	Difference	1043	246	-0.03	<0.01
		-0.01 (0.01)	0.02 (0.02)	(-0.07;0.01)	(-0.04;0.04)
Index	Item	1028	242		
	Before	0.92 (<0.01)	0.94 (0.01)		
	After	0.92 (<0.01)	0.93 (0.01)		
	Difference	1028	242	0.01	0.01
		<0.01 (<0.01)	-0.02 (0.01)	(-0.01;0.03)	(-0.01;0.03)
VAS	Item	1020	241		
	Before	84.64 (0.37)	86.41 (0.73)		
	After	84.05 (0.25)	87.36 (0.70)		
	Difference	1020	241	-1.53	-2.72
		-0.58 (0.35)	0.95 (0.62)	(-3.06;0.02)	(-4.53;-0.91)

EQ5D=EuroQol 5-dimension, SE=standard error, DID=difference-in-difference, CI=confidence interval, VAS=Visual analogue scale. Statistically significant differences at p<0.05 are bolded.

Table 5 The impact of surveillance for disease progression at specialised hospital clinic on quality of life for those with a positive screening test

		Surveillance	No surveillance	DID	
EQ5D		n	n	Unmatched	Matched
		mean (SE)	mean (SE)	mean (95% CI)	mean (95% CI)
Item	Before	112	3466		
		1.11 (0.03)	1.12 (0.01)		
	After	112	3466		
		1.20 (0.04)	1.14 (0.01)		
	Difference	112	3466	0.08	0.06
		0.09 (0.04)	0.01 (0.01)	(0.01;0.14)	(-0.03;0.15)
Index	Before	112	3410		
		0.86 (0.01)	0.90 (<0.01)		
	After	112	3410		
		0.84 (0.02)	0.88 (<0.01)		
	Difference	112	3410	-0.01	0.02
		-0.03 (0.01)	-0.02 (<0.01)	(-0.04;0.01)	(-0.01;0.06)
VAS	Before	110	3343		
		78.96 (1.39)	80.70 (0.26)		
	After	110	3343		
		76.42 (1.81)	80.49 (0.27)		
	Difference	110	3343	-2.33	-1.66
		-2.55 (1.40)	-0.22 (0.23)	(-4.82;0.18)	(-4.38;1.06)

EQ5D=EuroQol 5-dimension, SE=standard error, DID=difference-in-difference, CI=confidence interval, VAS=Visual analogue scale.

Statistically significant differences at p<0.05 are bolded.

Table 6 The impact of surgical repair on quality of life for those with indication for surveillance

		Surgical repair	No surgical repair	DID	
		n	n	Unmatched	Matched
EQ5D		mean (SE)	mean (SE)	mean (95% CI)	mean (95% CI)
Item	Before	72	604		
		1.22 (0.06)	1.15 (0.01)		
	After	72	604		
		1.19 (0.05)	1.15 (0.01)		
	Difference	72	604	-0.03	<0.01
		-0.03 (0.06)	<0.01 (0.01)	(-0.12;0.06)	(-0.13;0.13)
Index	Before	70	594		
		0.84 (0.02)	0.87 (0.01)		
	After	70	594		
		0.84 (0.03)	0.87 (0.01)		
	Difference	70	594	<0.01	<0.01
		<0.01 (0.02)	<0.00 (0.01)	(-0.03;0.04)	(-0.06;0.04)
VAS	Before	66	577		
		78.55 (2.04)	79.96 (0.61)		
	After	66	577		
		78.24 (2.40)	79.07 (0.67)		
	Difference	66	577	0.59	2.76
		-0.30 (2.15)	-0.89 (0.57)	(-3.03;4.22)	(-2.83;8.37)

EQ5D=EuroQol 5-dimension, SE=standard error, DID=difference-in-difference, CI=confidence interval, VAS=Visual analogue scale.

Statistically significant differences at p<0.05 are bolded.

Figure 1 Illustration of source populations in the quality-of-life survey piggy-backing on two screening trials generating the events of interest

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Appendix:

The impact of population screening for cardiovascular disease on quality of life: a difference-in-difference design using the EQ5D

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Table 1 Balancing of covariates after matching: impact of invitation

Item (n=19197)	Mean		% bias	t	p> t
	Treated	Control			
Living alone	0.170	0.170	0.000	0.000	1.000
Working	0.394	0.394	0.000	0.000	1.000
Income quartile 2	0.274	0.276	-0.600	-0.480	0.629
Income quartile 3	0.280	0.280	0.000	0.000	1.000
Income quartile 4	0.273	0.273	0.000	0.000	1.000
Global health	81.197	81.272	-0.500	-0.440	0.660
Profile index (n=19081)					
Living alone	0.169	0.169	0.000	0.000	1.000
Working	0.394	0.394	-0.100	-0.050	0.963
Income quartile 2	0.274	0.277	-0.600	-0.520	0.601
Income quartile 3	0.281	0.281	0.000	0.010	0.990
Income quartile 4	0.273	0.272	0.100	0.090	0.929
Global health	81.203	81.292	-0.600	-0.520	0.601
VAS (n=19242)					
Living alone	0.170	0.170	0.000	-0.030	0.976
Working	0.394	0.394	0.000	0.020	0.981
Income quartile 2	0.274	0.276	-0.500	-0.420	0.675
Income quartile 3	0.280	0.280	0.000	0.010	0.990
Income quartile 4	0.273	0.273	0.000	-0.040	0.970
Global health	81.196	81.291	-0.600	-0.560	0.575

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Table 2 Balancing of covariates after matching: impact of test result

Item (n=6826)	Mean		% bias	t	p> t
	Treated	Control			
Current smoker	0.179	0.175	1.000	0.400	0.686
Living alone	0.169	0.164	1.400	0.620	0.534
Working	0.404	0.396	1.700	0.790	0.431
Income quartile 2	0.274	0.278	-0.800	-0.370	0.711
Income quartile 3	0.285	0.287	-0.400	-0.200	0.845
Income quartile 4	0.273	0.269	1.000	0.500	0.620
Global health	80.273	80.343	-0.500	-0.210	0.830
Profile index (n=6715)					
Current smoker	0.180	0.174	1.500	0.610	0.540
Living alone	0.169	0.162	1.900	0.840	0.402
Working	0.406	0.395	2.200	1.000	0.318
Income quartile 2	0.275	0.267	1.800	0.800	0.423
Income quartile 3	0.285	0.289	-0.800	-0.340	0.731
Income quartile 4	0.273	0.276	-0.600	-0.270	0.784
Global health	80.276	80.149	0.900	0.380	0.704
VAS (n=6684)					
Current smoker	0.177	0.169	2.100	0.860	0.390
Living alone	0.166	0.156	2.800	1.220	0.223
Working	0.410	0.394	3.200	1.460	0.144
Income quartile 2	0.272	0.270	0.500	0.230	0.821
Income quartile 3	0.288	0.285	0.700	0.320	0.747
Income quartile 4	0.277	0.284	-1.500	-0.670	0.501
Global health	80.460	80.279	1.300	0.540	0.586

Table 3 Balancing of covariates after matching: impact of initiation of medication

Item (n=1289)	Mean		% bias	t	p> t
	Treated	Control			
Current smoker	0.208	0.176	8.500	1.900	0.058
Living alone	0.160	0.150	2.500	0.610	0.545
Working	0.485	0.454	6.200	1.410	0.159
Income quartile 2	0.230	0.263	-8.000	-1.780	0.075
Income quartile 3	0.294	0.263	6.800	1.570	0.117
Income quartile 4	0.324	0.340	-3.500	-0.790	0.428
Global health	84.504	84.516	-0.100	-0.020	0.984
Age	65.986	66.208	-5.9	-1.31	0.19
Profile index (n=1264)					
Current smoker	0.208	0.189	5.100	1.110	0.268
Living alone	0.161	0.156	1.500	0.360	0.716
Working	0.484	0.499	-2.900	-0.660	0.507
Income quartile 2	0.230	0.229	0.200	0.050	0.958
Income quartile 3	0.294	0.313	-4.300	-0.960	0.336
Income quartile 4	0.323	0.343	-4.400	-0.990	0.325
Global health	84.489	83.244	10.600	2.090	0.037
Age	65.985	65.887	2.6	0.57	0.57
VAS (n=1256)					
Current smoker	0.211	0.186	6.500	1.390	0.164
Living alone	0.160	0.135	6.500	1.570	0.118
Working	0.490	0.484	1.200	0.270	0.790
Income quartile 2	0.229	0.237	-2.100	-0.470	0.637
Income quartile 3	0.294	0.304	-2.400	-0.530	0.594
Income quartile 4	0.327	0.335	-1.700	-0.380	0.706
Global health	84.616	84.787	-1.500	-0.310	0.758
Age	65.954	66.07	-3.1	-0.68	0.493

Table 4 Balancing of covariates after matching: impact of enrolment in surveillance

Item (n=3558)	Mean		% bias	t	p> t
	Treated	Control			
Current smoker	0.205	0.241	-9.100	-0.640	0.523
Living alone	0.134	0.152	-5.000	-0.380	0.704
Working	0.196	0.205	-2.000	-0.170	0.868
Income quartile 2	0.366	0.366	0.000	0.000	1.000
Income quartile 3	0.330	0.366	-7.700	-0.560	0.577
Income quartile 4	0.188	0.116	16.900	1.490	0.138
Global health	79.116	79.018	0.700	0.050	0.959
Age	69.232	69.295	-1.8	-0.15	0.878
Profile index (n=3502)					
Current smoker	0.205	0.205	0.000	0.000	1.000
Living alone	0.134	0.116	5.000	0.400	0.688
Working	0.196	0.196	0.000	0.000	1.000
Income quartile 2	0.366	0.313	11.600	0.840	0.399
Income quartile 3	0.330	0.339	-1.900	-0.140	0.888
Income quartile 4	0.188	0.188	0.000	0.000	1.000
Global health	79.116	78.598	3.500	0.260	0.793
Age	69.232	69.42	-5.3	-0.47	0.641
VAS (n=3438)					
Current smoker	0.200	0.200	0.000	0.000	1.000
Living alone	0.127	0.145	-5.200	-0.390	0.696
Working	0.182	0.182	0.000	0.000	1.000
Income quartile 2	0.373	0.355	3.900	0.280	0.780
Income quartile 3	0.336	0.355	-3.900	-0.280	0.778
Income quartile 4	0.173	0.145	6.500	0.550	0.582
Global health	78.964	79.527	-3.800	-0.300	0.767
Age	69.227	69.318	-2.6	-0.22	0.828

Table 5 Balancing of covariates after matching: impact of surgical repair

Item (n=674)	Mean		% bias	t	p> t
	Treated	Control			
Current smoker	0.229	0.329	-24.100	-1.320	0.190
Living alone	0.200	0.186	3.600	0.210	0.832
Working	0.286	0.171	25.400	1.610	0.109
Income quartile 2	0.243	0.214	6.300	0.400	0.690
Income quartile 3	0.314	0.314	0.000	0.000	1.000
Income quartile 4	0.200	0.229	-7.000	-0.410	0.683
Global health	76.771	76.843	-0.400	-0.020	0.980
Age	68.843	69.086	-7	-0.39	0.7
Profile index (n=662)					
Current smoker	0.235	0.176	14.100	0.840	0.400
Living alone	0.206	0.132	18.700	1.140	0.256
Working	0.294	0.324	-6.500	-0.370	0.713
Income quartile 2	0.235	0.250	-3.300	-0.200	0.843
Income quartile 3	0.324	0.382	-12.900	-0.710	0.477
Income quartile 4	0.191	0.206	-3.600	-0.210	0.831
Global health	77.118	76.809	1.900	0.100	0.917
Age	68.809	69.044	-6.7	-0.39	0.697
VAS (n=641)					
Current smoker	0.250	0.141	26.000	1.560	0.120
Living alone	0.188	0.266	-20.200	-1.050	0.295
Working	0.281	0.328	-10.400	-0.570	0.568
Income quartile 2	0.250	0.188	13.800	0.850	0.396
Income quartile 3	0.313	0.359	-10.300	-0.560	0.578
Income quartile 4	0.203	0.203	0.000	0.000	1.000
Global health	78.813	80.203	-9.000	-0.510	0.611
Age	68.984	69.078	-2.7	-0.15	0.88

Figure 1 Propensity scores for the invitation for screening

Note: the individual scores are estimated in the samples responding to each of the individual scales of the EQ5D: a) anxiety/depression item, b) profile index, c) VAS

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Figure 2 Propensity scores for screening test result

Note: the individual scores are estimated in the samples responding to each of the individual scales of the EQ5D: a) anxiety/depression item, b) profile index, c) VAS

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Figure 3 Propensity scores for initiation of preventive medication

Note: the individual scores are estimated in the samples responding to each of the individual scales of the EQ5D: a) anxiety/depression item, b) profile index, c) VAS

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Figure 4 Propensity scores for enrolment in surveillance

Note: the individual scores are estimated in the samples responding to each of the individual scales of the EQ5D: a) anxiety/depression item, b) profile index, c) VAS

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Figure 5 Propensity scores for surgical repair

Note: the individual scores are estimated in the samples responding to each of the individual scales of the EQ5D: a) anxiety/depression item, b) profile index, c) VAS

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